

PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS ASSESSMENT CRITERIA OF QUALITY ACTIVITY OF STAFF TRAINING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article describes the prospects of developing the skills of future specialists studying in the credit module system of a higher educational institution. In addition, the structure of improving the quality of the educational system was developed by the author as a model for organizing students' classes. ушбу Мақоллада олий таълим муассасаси kredit modul tizimda ta'lim olayotgan бўлажак мутахассисларни ta'lim sifat baholash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish шқ yoritilgan. Bundan tashqari, muallif tomonidan talabalarning dars mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishda ta'lim tizimi sifatini oshirish strukturasi namuna sifatida ishlab chiqilgan.

Keywords: Quality, element, material-technology, process, component, development, structure, credit module.

Kalit so'zlar: Sifat, element, moddiy-texnika, jarayon, tarkibiy qism, rivojlantirish, struktura, kredit modul.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", the implementation of the tasks defined in the Development Strategy and State Programs, as well as the adoption of a number of laws and by-laws on education fundamentally changed the content of education. To develop and implement measures in accordance with the unified state policy in the system of higher education, to analyze and study the forms of methodologies that ensure the uniform quality of education in accordance with international standards, as well as to establish a mechanism for analyzing problems in the field of education and finding appropriate solutions for them, to develop this field the development of targeted proposals has become one of the most pressing issues today.

Today, the following trends are playing a leading role in the management of the quality of personnel training in a higher education institution:

1. Development of uniform criteria and standards guaranteeing the quality of education in European countries within the framework of Bologna processes;
2. Creation, development and harmonization of the national system of accreditation of educational programs of European countries;
3. TQM - the concept of total quality management, development and implementation of the quality system of the higher education institution based on the International ISO 9000:2000, ENQA (European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education), the model of the European Foundation for Quality Management and other national models;
4. Таълим жараёни сифатини бошқариш тизимини сифатни ялпи бошқариш концепцияси тамойиллари асосида ташкил этиш;
5. Transition from external control of the quality of the educational process and its results based on the national attestation and accreditation system to the internal self-assessment system of the educational institution based on one or another selected model;
6. Taking into account that although external control has achieved significant success in terms of normative and scientific provision, it does not allow to fully identify existing problems and achievements, and plan to improve the quality of education, due to the fact that it is based on the determination of quantitative indicators in an episodic manner. [32. 92 p.].

Decree No. PF-6097 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 29, 2020 on the approval of the Concept of Science Development until 2030 was adopted.

In the concept of development of science until 2030 (hereinafter referred to as the Concept) and the target indicators and indicators of the Concept, a strategic plan aimed at the development of human capital in achieving the ambitious goal of including Uzbekistan in the global innovation index ranking by 2030 among the 50 leading countries of the world was announced. This goal is to adapt the field of science to the requirements of the modern economy, and in turn, it is aimed at implementing fundamental structural, organizational, financial, personnel and infrastructure reforms in science regulated by the appropriate legal framework.

In recent years, more than 20 normative legal documents aimed at the priority development of the science sector and state support have been adopted, and they are based on the principles of continuity, openness, transparency and competition.

10 scientific organizations of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education were returned to the system of the Academy of Sciences, while increasing its status and prestige, the position of the field of science in society was increased, and the attitude of young people to the field changed in a positive direction.

At the same time, the following 19 main problems that need to be solved in the field of science in the near future remain:

- Thirteenth, it was pointed out that the relations between scientific organizations and higher education institutions are weak, and the solid integration of education, science and production is not ensured.

§ 5 of the decree. Also in paragraph 4 of the section on the formation of a modern information environment that supports the development of science:

- assessment of the country's scientific and technical potential: analysis of the state of science and trends in its further development, study of the qualitative and quantitative development of our country's science in recent years, to identify and analyze the strengths and weaknesses of the local scientific and technical potential, to analyze the effectiveness of the activities of scientific organizations and higher education institutions and the development of scientific infrastructure, to study the mechanisms of scientific research and experimental design work that affect socio-economic development, to study the scientific research programs work will be carried out to improve the efficiency and effectiveness evaluation system he stated.

What is the main goal of developing the skills of evaluating the quality of education of vocational students in the higher education system? The concept of development of science until 2030- consists in adapting the field of science to the requirements of the modern economy, ensuring the integration of science and production, and training quality personnel for production. (Figure -1).

Also, one of the urgent issues is the development and introduction of objective evaluation criteria and indicators based on quality criteria in ensuring and determining the quality of students' knowledge in the higher education system.

Figure 1. Integration of science, education and production in training quality personnel for production.

The normative criteria of higher education, its resources, are working as a management system and criterion of the higher education quality system (Table 1) at the level of the demand and stage of personnel training in higher education institutions.

Curricula and educational programs of higher education baccalaureate courses are developed on the basis of state education standards of higher education, qualification requirements of baccalaureate courses, ensuring consistency and continuity with general secondary and secondary special, professional education. Curriculum includes a block of compulsory subjects (compulsory subjects) and a block of optional subjects (elective subjects).

In mastering the curricula and educational programs of undergraduate courses, it should be assumed that, along with classroom training, students should perform independent training in academic subjects and receive independent knowledge.

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